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Emulsion Concept, Types and Techniques: A Review

**Chiwuike Dominic Ogbonna^{1,*}, Obioma Uzoma Njoku^{1,2},
Chinedu Christian Iheanacho³, Geraldine Amarachi Chukwu⁴,
Racheal Adaeze Orié⁵ and Chizurum Ezinwanyi Ogbonna⁶**

¹ Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Biological Sciences, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria

² College of Postgraduate Studies, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria

³ Department of Microbiology, Faculty of BioSciences, Federal University Wukari, Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

⁴ Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Faculty of Health Sciences, Veritas University, Abuja, Nigeria

⁵ Department of Food Science and Technology, Faculty of Agriculture and Natural Resource Management, Ebonyi State University, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

⁶ Department of Chemistry/Industrial Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Imo State University, Imo State, Nigeria

*E-mail address: cdogbonna@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The concept of emulsion is very important in many industries such as nutritional, pharmaceutical, cosmetics and life in general. Generally, emulsions are stabilized by emulsifiers, which do not only confer stability on the products but also nutrition, aesthetics, and durability. While creating an emulsion from two separate immiscible liquids and with respect to the desired type, it is also important to note that the best emulsification techniques must be applied. This review therefore summarizes the concept of emulsions, and presents a critical discussion of their types and preparation techniques. Moreover, insights into the strategic approach for optimizing emulsion preparation techniques for meaningful practical applications are provided. It is therefore expected that this review will be of significant impact in the development of new emulsions for industrial applications.

Keywords: Emulsification, Emulsifier, Emulsion, HLB

1. INTRODUCTION

An emulsion refers to a heterogeneous system consisting of a close mixture of two immiscible liquids, one dispersed in the other in drop form (Oliveira *et al.*, 2011; Singh and Pulikkal, 2024). The former is called the dispersed, internal or discontinuous phase and occurs as droplets dispersed within the other liquid, the continuous or external phase. Macroemulsions, nanoemulsions and microemulsions are the different categories of emulsions. Their main distinguishing features are in droplet size range and stability characteristics (Gupta *et al.*, 2016). The classical emulsion droplet diameters are typically of the order of 0.1 to 100 μm , but may be as small as a few nanometres or as large as many hundreds of micrometres, and are stabilized by surface active agents (McClements and Weiss, 2005; Kupikowska-Stobba *et al.*, 2024).

Many natural and processed products contain small droplets of oil dispersed in an aqueous medium or vice versa. Emulsification leading to processed products is targeted to give a single or set of desired product quality such as sensory properties depending on the size distribution of the droplets (Håkansson, 2019). Despite the considerable diversity of physicochemical and sensory characteristics exhibited by these products, they can all be considered to fall into a class of material called “emulsions” and their properties can be understood using the concepts and techniques of “emulsion science”, which is multidisciplinary (McClements and Weiss, 2005).

Emulsion process help reduce certain challenges in effective handling (against rancidity, for example) of oils. For instance, emulsification, which is basically a physical modification process, helps to maintain, to a very large extent, the chemical integrity of the oil in the dispersion system (as the liquids are immiscible) unlike in hydrogenation. Hydrogenation is a modification process that alters both the physical and chemical states of the oil and by such, adversely affects the end usage. If partial, hydrogenation could result in the production of trans-fatty acids (TFAs), which impart good physical and chemical properties, in industrial-scale food production (e.g., extended shelf-life, solid at room temperature, high flash point, etc.) but have a negative impact on the human cardiovascular system (Ascherio *et al.*, 1999).

Emulsions have different types, production processes, constituents, properties, stabilities and uses. In this review, the general concept about emulsions and its constituents are discussed in detail. First, a compendious discussion about the various types of emulsions is presented. Second, the role of emulsifiers in the generation of emulsions are presented. Third, we detailed some of the available techniques for preparing emulsions. Finally, we drew conclusions from the discussions and presented a future perspective for achieving stable emulsions for practical applications.

2. TYPES OF EMULSIONS

Emulsions can be classified according to different criteria. In the classic type of emulsion or broad sense, the two immiscible liquids involved are water and oil. Simple emulsions are oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion, where the oil is the dispersed phase, and water is the dispersion medium; and water-in-oil (W/O) emulsion, where water is the dispersed phase and oil is the external phase. Multiple or double emulsions, which could be referred to as complex emulsions are also possible; including a "water-in-oil-in-water" (W1/O/W2) emulsion and an "oil-in-water-in-oil" (O1/W/O2) emulsion, where W1 (respectively O1) and W2 (respectively O2) indicate the most internal phase and the most external one respectively.

These multiple emulsions may have advantages over traditional emulsions for certain applications, e.g., fat reduction, controlled ingredient release, or isolation of one ingredient from another (Dickinson and McClements, 1995). Another type of emulsion is the biemulsion, containing two different internal phase droplets, either of the same nature but different size or of different nature, whatever the size is (Salager, 2000).

Additionally, emulsions can be categorized under micro- and nanoemulsions based on their respective droplet sizes. The former is the type of emulsion described earlier as having droplet diameter of the order of 0.1 to 100 μm (Tan and McClements, 2021) while nanoemulsions are special emulsions that consist of very small drops with size between 20 to 500 nm (Solans *et al.*, 2003; Nakajima *et al.*, 1993; Kupikowska-Stobba *et al.*, 2024) and 50 to 200 nm (Tadros *et al.*, 2004). Nanoemulsions also have simple and complex formations.

Among the complex nanoemulsions are the nanostructured multiple emulsions and multilayered emulsions. For example, a nanostructured W1/O/W2 emulsion would consist of nanometer-sized water droplets or reverse micelles (W1) contained within larger oil droplets (O) that are dispersed within an aqueous continuous phase (W2) (Weiss *et al.*, 2006).

Nanostructured multilayered systems typically consist of oil droplets (the core) surrounded by nanometer thick layers (the shell) comprised of different polyelectrolytes (Weiss *et al.*, 2006). These layers are formed using a layer-by-layer (LbL) electrostatic deposition method that involves sequential adsorption of polyelectrolytes onto the surfaces of oppositely charged colloidal particles. Figure 1 shows an example of the LbL approach to encapsulating oil droplets in an O/W emulsion.

3. EMULSION CONSTITUENTS

Generally, emulsions are made from several materials based on their application area; but basically, consist of three main constituents, namely; an aqueous phase, oil phase and emulsifier. The physicochemical properties of these phases and the emulsifier determine the overall physicochemical property of the emulsion (Salager, 2000; McClements and Weiss, 2005; Tan and McClements, 2021).

A) Aqueous Phase

The aqueous phase of an emulsion is the water and/or hydrophilic solvent used to prepare the emulsion. It is usually prepared with distilled or deionized water of which either can stand alone as an aqueous phase. The aqueous phase of an emulsion may contain a wide variety of components, including minerals, acids, bases, biopolymers, sugars, alcohols, ice crystals, flavors, preservatives, vitamins, surfactants, proteins or polysaccharides and gas bubbles (McClements and Weiss, 2005; Molet-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2018).

B) Oil Phase

The oil phase is the oil and/or lipophilic ingredients contained in an emulsion. These ingredients include colors, antioxidants, phospholipids, carotenes, fat-soluble vitamins, plant essential oils among others (Molet-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2018). The oil phase could be in a fluid state (for example in food emulsions like milk, coffee whiteners, and dressings) or in (partially) crystalline state (for example, ice cream mixes, whipping cream) (Granger *et al.*, 2003).

C) Emulsifiers

Emulsifiers are those surfactants that are specifically used to stabilize emulsions by lowering interfacial tension and inhibiting aggregation of droplets (McClements and Weiss, 2005; Mushtaq *et al.*, 2023). They contain a nonpolar, and one or more polar regions. Generally, nonpolar groups are aliphatic, alicyclic, or aromatic hydrocarbons. The polar region, which contains heteroatoms such as oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur impact functionality. The polar functionality makes the emulsifier anionic, cationic, amphoteric, or nonionic. Emulsifiers are amphiphilic molecules, owing to their hydrophilic head and hydrophobic tail.

Their amphiphilic nature enables them to orient at interfaces, a reason for their surface activity. Emulsifiers tend to promote dispersion of the dispersed phase in the continuous phase, as well as the arrangement of the phases in an emulsion, that is, which phase will form the dispersed versus continuous phase (Schramm *et al.*, 2003). This depends on the solubility of the emulsifiers in both phases, which is better described and predicted by their hydrophile–lipophile balance (HLB), a system proposed by W.C. Griffin in 1949 for non-ionic surfactants (Dingcong, 2002).

HLB is a measure of the ratio of the hydrophilic head group to the lipophilic tail (McClements and Weiss, 2005). HLB values are very useful in order to select a surfactant for a particular application and are often listed by the surfactant manufacturer (Table 1).

Figure 1. Schematic for formation of a number of nanolayers around particles (Weiss *et al.*, 2006).

This dimensionless scale ranges from 0 to 20 for non-ionic surfactants; a low HLB (<9) refers to a lipophilic surfactant (oil soluble) and a high HLB (>11) to a hydrophilic (water soluble) surfactant. Most ionic surfactants have HLB values greater than 20. Some examples of

surfactant HLBs are given in Table 2. In general, water-in-oil (W/O) emulsifiers exhibit HLB values in the range 3–8 while oil-in-water (O/W) emulsifiers have HLB values of about 8–18 (Schramm *et al.*, 2003).

Table 1. Applications and corresponding HLB values (McClements and Weiss, 2005).

HLB Range	Application
<3	Surface films Water-in-oil emulsifiers
3–6	Water-in-oil emulsifiers
7–9	Wetting agents
8–15	Oil-in-water emulsifiers
13–15	Detergents
15–18	Solubilizers

Table 2. Approximate surfactant HLB values (Schramm *et al.*, 2003).

Surfactant	HLB
Oleic acid	1
Sorbitan tristearate (SPAN 65)	2
Sorbitan monooleate (SPAN 80)	4
Diethylene glycol monolaurate	6
Sorbitan monolaurate (SPAN 20)	9
Glycerol monostearate	11
Polyoxyethylene (10) cetyl ether (BRIJ 56)	13
Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate (TWEEN 80)	15
Sodium octadecanoate	18
Sodium dodecanoate	21
Sodium octanoate	23
Diethyl sodium sulfosuccinate	32
Sodium heptadecyl sulfate	38
Sodium dodecyl sulfate	40
Sodium octyl sulfate	42

Emulsifiers are often classified under two major groups, namely; nonionic and ionic emulsifiers. A nonionic surfactant contains no formal positive or negative charge, but a polar

heteroatom produces a dipole with an electron dense and electron-depleted region (Hasenhuettl, 2008). Nonionic emulsifiers are the principal surfactants encountered in food systems.

They have several advantages over ionic surfactants as the former are usually considered to be relatively safe and better tolerated in comparison to the later (Liu and Lunter, 2020). Nonionic can cover a wide range of HLB values and are more environmentally friendly because they are easily biodegradable. Examples of nonionic emulsifiers include the Span® and Tween® surfactants (Table 2) (Schramm *et al.*, 2003).

Within the ionic group, there are two main sub-categories: anionic and cationic emulsifiers. An anionic emulsifier contains a negative charge on the bulky molecule, associated with a small positive counterion. Anionic surfactants make about 75% of all the consumption of surface-active material (McClements and Weiss, 2005). They are rarely encountered in the preparation of an actual food. The toxicity level of anionic surfactants is high and even small doses of anionic surfactants can cause allergic reactions and nausea (McClements and Weiss, 2005; Chen *et al.*, 2020). However, as they are very strong detergents, they can be used to solubilize components such as proteins. Due to their strong electrostatic repulsion, they are also very effective in stabilizing emulsions and are therefore often applied in technical emulsions such as emulsified lubricants. Sodium dodecylsulphate (SDS), carboxylated soaps and esters of phosphoric acid are examples of anionic emulsifiers. SDS is probably the best-studied surfactant. SDS, a sulphate ester, is an extremely effective emulsifier because of its high-electrostatic repulsion (Schramm *et al.*, 2003).

Table 3. Classification of emulsifying agents based on the presence of formally charged groups in their heads (Khan *et al.*, 2011).

S/N	Surfactant class	Surface charge	Example
01	Anionic (based on sulfate, sulfonate or carboxylate anions)	The charge is negative	Perfluorooctanoate (PFOA or PFO) Perfluorooctanesulfonate (PFOS) Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), ammonium lauryl sulfate, and other alkyl sulfate salts Sodium laureth sulfate, also known as sodium lauryl ether sulfate (SLES) Alkyl benzene sulfonate Soaps, or fatty acid salts
02	Cationic (based on quaternary ammonium cations)	The charge is positive	Cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) a.k.a. hexadecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, and other alkyltrimethylammonium salts Cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) Polyethoxylated tallow amine (POEA) Benzalkonium chloride (BAC) Benzethonium chloride (BZT)
03	Zwitterionic (amphoteric)	Two oppositely charged groups	Dodecyl betaine Cocamidopropyl betaine Coco amphoteric glycinate

04	Nonionic	No charge groups	Alkyl poly(ethylene oxide) Alkylphenol poly(ethylene oxide) Copolymers of poly(ethylene oxide) and poly(propylene oxide) (commercially called Poloxamers or Poloxamines) Alkyl polyglucosides, including: octyl glucoside and decyl maltoside Fatty alcohols, including: cetyl alcohol and oleyl alcohol Cocamide MEA Polysorbates, including: Tween 20 and Tween 80
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Cationics have a positively charged molecule with a negative counterion. Cationic emulsifiers are components in fungicides (Fait *et al.*, 2019) and germicides. Their strong bacteriostatic properties make them recognized as important sanitizing and antiseptic agents. Examples of cationic emulsifiers are found in Table 3. There are also amphoteric emulsifiers, which contain both positive and negative charges on the same molecule, for example, dodecyl betaine.

While emulsifiers are used to achieve stability and promote dispersion, other formulating constituents of emulsions are introduced into the system for various reasons, including nutrition, aesthetics, and durability. For instance, minerals, acids, bases, vitamins, flavours, colorants, amongst others are used in producing certain food emulsions (McClements and Weiss, 2005).

4. EMULSION PREPARATION TECHNIQUES

The process of creating an emulsion from two separate immiscible liquids, or of reducing the size of the droplets in a preexisting emulsion, is called homogenization (McClements and Weiss, 2005). This process is also known as emulsification. Emulsification does not tend to occur spontaneously. There is often an energy input. External energy must, therefore, be supplied to form an emulsion (Håkansson and Rayner, 2018).

Several procedures may be applied for emulsion preparation, ranging from simple pipe flow (low agitation energy, L), static mixers and general stirrers (low to medium energy, L–M), high-speed mixers such as the Ultra-Turrax (M), colloid mills and high-pressure homogenizers (high energy, H), and ultrasound generators (M–H) (Tadros, 2009; Malode *et al.*, 2021). Spontaneous emulsification can also occur when the phases are in contact (Miller, 1988) and can also occur, for example, by chemical reactions (Nishimi and Miller, 2001).

Ultrasonication, rotor–stators, static mixers, and membrane emulsification are the most frequently used methods (Kiss *et al.*, 2011; Malode *et al.*, 2021).

A) Static Mixing

Static mixers consist of motionless mixer elements with cross- bars fitted in a housing tube. Flow in such mixers may be laminar or turbulent. Mixing in these systems is achieved by dividing and re-uniting fluid streams. Unit operations using static mixers are the blending of fluids, heat transfer, and solids blending. Multiphase applications operating with static mixers

are the blending of a continuous liquid phase and a dispersed gas or immiscible liquid phase (Etchells III and Meyer, 2004).

Ultra Turrax is an example of rotor-stator homogenizer. It has an emulsifying head with blades which are surrounded by stainless steel fine mesh sieves. The emulsifying head is adjustable for insertion into the containers to be used for emulsification. An electric motor rotates the head while the liquid to be emulsified is sucked by the fine mesh sieve into the emulsifying head where they are subjected to intense mixing due to the rotation of blades of emulsifying head. Adjustable process factor such as speed (in rounds per minutes – rpm) is important in setting up the rotor-stator.

B) Membrane Emulsification

In conventional direct membrane emulsification, fine droplets are formed at the membrane/continuous phase interface by pressing the disperse phase through the membrane (Charcosset, 2009). In order to ensure a regular droplet detachment from the pore outlets, shear stress is generated at the membrane/continuous phase interface by recirculating the continuous phase using a pump or by agitation in a stirring vessel (Vladisavljevic' and Williams, 2005). Membrane emulsification involves using a low pressure to force the dispersed phase to permeate through a membrane into the continuous phase. The distinguishing feature is that the resulting droplet size is controlled primarily by the choice of the membrane and not by the generation of turbulent droplet break-up. The technique is highly attractive given its simplicity, potentially lower energy demands, need for less surfactant and the resulting narrow droplet size distributions. It is applicable to o/w, w/o and multiple emulsions (Joscelyne and Trägårdh, 2000; Charcosset *et al.*, 2004; Vladisavljevic and Williams, 2005).

Membrane Emulsification (ME) is a relatively new technique for producing single and multiple emulsions for Drug Delivery Systems (DDS), solid micro carriers for drug or nutrient encapsulation, solder particles for surface-mount technology, and mono distributed polymer microspheres for analytical column packing, enzyme carriers, liquid crystal display spacers, and toner core particles (Qinglin, 2022). ME also finds applications in the dairy industry (close to 40%, of which over 10% are used for milk protein standardization), beverages (wine, beer, fruit and vegetable juices and concentrates), egg products (2%), waste streams, co-products (recovery and recycling of blood plasma in abattoirs), and technical fluids (brines, cleaning-in-place solutions) (Charcosset, 2009; Ali *et al.*, 2022; Huang *et al.*, 2024).

C) Ultrasound Emulsification

Ultrasound is a sound wave with a frequency above the human audible range (16 Hz to 16 kHz) (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2009). Ultrasound may be broadly classified according to frequency range as power ultrasound (20–100 kHz) and diagnostic ultrasound (1–10 MHz). Power ultrasound enhances the rate of various physical and chemical processes in a liquid medium through the generation and subsequent collapse of cavitation bubbles. Power ultrasound is commonly employed for enhancing the physical processes such as cleaning, emulsification, degassing, crystallisation, extraction, etc., and for accelerating/performing chemical reactions (Contamine *et al.*, 1994; Sivakumar and Rao, 2003).

Ultrasound is known to enhance the emulsification and dispersion of oils/fat (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2003). Ultrasound has been employed successfully for emulsification of oils/fat and in the preparation of fatliquor emulsion with reduction in emulsion particle-size (Sivakumar *et al.*,

2008, Malode *et al.*, 2021). The ultrasound activity arises mainly from acoustic cavitation in liquid media, which are nucleation, growth and explosive collapse of microbubbles on a microsecond time-scale (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2009). The intense agitation and dispersion effect, which is brought out by the effects of cavitation, results in an increase in the number of collisions between the fat particles and the water and hence better emulsification of fat in water (Sivakumar *et al.*, 2009).

In the fatliquoring process, oils/fats are employed as oil in water emulsion known as fatliquor. The potential use of ultrasound in such stage of leather processing is aimed at improving the quality, diffusion rate, and to reduce process time and pollution load (Xie *et al.*, 2000; Sivakumar and Rao, 2003). Fatliquor may be anionic, cationic or non-ionic. Anionic fatliquors are commonly employed for fat binding with chrome-tanned leather, which is cationically charged (Xie *et al.*, 2000).

5. CONCLUSION

Emulsions consist of small droplets of an immiscible liquid dispersed in another, and have different types, based on the two immiscible liquids used for the production, and the droplet size. Emulsifiers play an important role in stabilizing emulsions and this depends on the emulsifiers' solubility in both phases as predicted by their HLB. While emulsifiers are used to achieve stability and promote dispersion, other formulating constituents of emulsions are introduced into the system for various reasons, including nutrition, aesthetics, and durability. Several procedures may be applied for emulsion preparation, ranging from simple pipe flow (low agitation energy, L), static mixers and general stirrers (low to medium energy, L–M), high-speed mixers such as the Ultra-Turrax (M), colloid mills and high-pressure homogenizers (high energy, H), and ultrasound generators (M–H).

A lot of studies are needed in emulsion science for various applications purposes and this can be achieved by in-depth research in the various constituents that make-up an emulsion.

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